

Equitable & Inclusive Team Science

Authors

Bethan Iley, OLS & Queen's University Belfast; **Flávio Azevedo**, the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT) & Utrecht University; **Arielle Bennett**, The Alan Turing Institute; **Polat Goktas**, UCD School of Computer Science & Ireland's Centre for Applied Artificial Intelligence (CeADAR), University College Dublin; **Dominik Kiersz**, independent engineer; **Mayya Sundukova**, OLS & University of Extremadura; **Ahmed Unshur**, Institute for Globally Distributed Open Research and Education (IGDORE) & City University of Mogadishu; **Yo Yehudi**, OLS.

Details of contributions are listed on the associated [Tenzing sheet](#). Correspondence should be addressed to Yo Yehudi (yo@we-are-ols.org).

Summary of the Work

In the UK, certain groups (e.g. women; Gypsy, Roma and Travellers; disabled people) are underrepresented in **STEM**, particularly at the most senior levels ¹. This includes within **data science**, an **interdisciplinary** field which combines computer science and statistics. On a global scale, individuals from **LMICs** are also underrepresented ². **DEI&A** policies aim to correct these imbalances.

Academic STEM fields have been adopting **open science**, whereby scientific practice is documented accurately and transparently. Open science practices include registering analysis plans in advance of conducting research (e.g. pre-registration ³), publicly sharing data through online repositories (e.g., ESO Data Archives ⁴), and documenting who contributed to each part of the scientific process (e.g. using the Contributor Roles Taxonomy ⁵).

One development linked to open science is **team science**, in which many collaborators across institutions, fields and sectors work together to address a single research question ⁶. Team science projects result in large datasets collected across multiple sites worldwide. Equitable and inclusive team science has the potential to facilitate sharing resources and expertise with individuals from underrepresented backgrounds ⁷.

Working with large datasets is a fundamental aspect of data scientists' skill sets, yet they are rarely invited to participate in team science projects. Furthermore, team science projects may not consider the DEI&A considerations of their work; this could impact underrepresented groups' access to team science opportunities, as well as resulting in a less diverse (and therefore less generalisable) dataset.

The present research aimed to map the intersection between DEI&A, team science and data science, with a focus on the policies which facilitate equitable and inclusive team science. To do this, we conducted a three-stage research project:

(1) Policy review of written policies from research organisations active in the UK, including universities, funding bodies, and international team science consortia.

(2) A workshop with individuals who have experience in team science, DEI&A,

and/or data science. Participants were asked about the interface between the three areas of interest and existing *de jure* and *de facto* policy related to their work. Participants then collaboratively identified areas for future policy development.

(3) A survey allowing anyone to contribute their ideas for equitable and inclusive team science policy. This was to combat **survivorship bias** as underrepresented groups may not meet the workshop inclusion criteria.

Key Findings

(1) Policy Review

In our policy review, we could not find any policies which address all three topics. The reviewed international organisation, university, and funder policies did not mention team science. Where organisations had their own widening participation or DEI&A policy, team science was never considered.

(2) Workshop

The workshop findings could be summarised into three key areas:

(2.1) Existing Practice in Industry

Participants reported that private companies have a mix of *de jure* DEI&A workplace policies, such as childcare support or parental leave, and *de facto* policies, such as team leads having implicit responsibility for ensuring equity within their team.

Industry data workers, including data scientists, primarily considered *de jure* policies around data protection. These are often strict to comply with national or

international requirements (e.g. GDPR, HIPAA). In turn, these dictate rules for data management such as encryption, deletion requests, and internal access to data. In cloud infrastructure, automated governance systems can perform auditing to assess compliance (e.g., Azure Policy⁸).

(2.2) Existing Practice in Academia

Participants reported that research institutions and funders often have strong *de jure* DEI&A policies for staff and students (e.g. EPSRC⁹). Individual research groups sometimes have *de facto* policies in addition to institutional or organisational policies.

Some *de jure* policies exist to support public engagement with STEM, but these reflect a focus on communication rather than inclusion. For example, there may be policies to support science communication activities, but not to facilitate participants **co-producing** research (such as by covering travel costs). NIHR's approach to Patient and Public Involvement¹⁰ was highlighted as a positive example in this area.

Participants reported that some institutions require individuals to report DEI&A information alongside research ethics committee applications.

(2.3) Barriers to Implementation

Unclear terminology. Several participants were unsure of the semantics of team science. It was noted that "team science", "big team science", "large collaborations" and "consortia" are all used interchangeably.

Lack of structured support. Participants reported that team science grassroots

organisations are rarely given support by larger research or funding institutions to develop their own policies. There is little documentation, but what exists is shared between organisations and edited to match each mission or vision.

Barriers to collaboration. There was general support for interdisciplinary and **cross-sector collaboration**, although multiple participants reported barriers to engaging in these styles of work. For example, organisational policies can create inefficiencies or prevent collaboration entirely. Policy context varies quite significantly across countries. Research and policies to develop international collaborations are required, but specific recommendations beyond the scope of this research.

Inconsistent data capture. It was noted that some types of diversity data are widely recorded, but others (e.g. socio-economic background, career stage or seniority) are rarely captured.

(3) Survey

Data collection for the survey is underway as of April 2024, but preliminary results support the findings of the workshop.

Policy Recommendations

(1) Facilitate Collaborative Research

Interdisciplinary and cross-sector working should be the default assumption for team science projects. Work is needed to identify the key academic and corporate stakeholders in relation to all aspects of research (e.g. ethics, methodology) and how their inclusion would benefit research quality.

Future policies should: remove identified barriers and develop guidelines to facilitate interoperable and international standards of collaboration.

(2) Invest in Operational Capacity

Research organisations and funding bodies must support team science projects to develop documentation regarding project management, DEI&A, and interdisciplinary or cross-sector working. This should include funding team science projects to develop their operational capacity.

Scientists would benefit from updated training which reflects modern collaborative practices. This could include updated training in research integrity which includes DEI&A principles from project conception; data governance for sharing data within large cross-sector teams; and infrastructure, such as promoting best practices used in IT and data industries, such as using data access auditing.

(3) Standardise DEI&A Practices

National guidelines are needed on the capturing of diversity data which are more difficult to quantify, such as socio-economic background and migration status.

Likewise, national guidelines and standards must be developed to support researchers to consider DEI&A at all stages of research projects, for all methodologies and academic fields. This must include specific recommendations for team science projects which reflect their unique characteristics.

Policies and guidelines should include plain language summaries by default to ensure accessibility.

Biases and stereotypes may impact DEI&A in data science and team science. More research is needed to identify these impacts, such as how a lack of diversity creates biases in datasets.

Additional Information (links, references)

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Glossary

Co-production. Collaborative work which produces some kind of output. In research, this often refers to participatory methods which include participants as co-researchers.

Cross-sector collaboration. When two or more organisations from different sectors work together. For example, researchers at a university may collaborate with researchers in a private research and development department.

Data science. An academic discipline and professional field which uses interdisciplinary techniques to manipulate and analyse data. Data scientists often work with large datasets and apply a range of techniques, such as machine learning algorithms.

De facto policy. Policy that happens, whether or not it is official. Unspoken rules for things are done.

DEI&A. An acronym for diversity, equity, inclusion and accessibility.

De jure policy. Official policy, whether or not it is enforced.

Generalisability. Whether the results of research can be applied to a broader population.

Interdisciplinarity. Research based on methodologies or knowledge generated by multiple fields.

LMICs. An acronym for Low to Middle Income Countries.

Open science. A philosophy and set of practices which prioritise transparency in science. Examples of open science practices include sharing data on public repositories and open access publications.

Survivorship bias. Assuming that individuals who met selection criteria are representative of the whole population, even where they are not.

STEM. An acronym for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Team science. Scientific research projects which bring together a large number of collaborators, often by pooling resources and working in an interdisciplinary nature. The largest projects are sometimes referred to as big team science.